

Commons Clinic
Wholebody
Assessment:
Early Findings
and Future
Directions

© Commons Clinic 2025

Commons Clinic *Wholebody* Assessment: Early Findings and Future Directions

Authors: Benjamin Schwartz, MD, MBA, Jenica Ortega, MD, Faith Gutierrez, MSN, RN,
Nicholas Aubin, BS
Commons Clinic 2901 Wilshire Blvd., Suite 300, Santa Monica, CA 90403

Executive Summary

- **Purpose:** Establish a novel, comprehensive prevention, detection, and early intervention health assessment and gather early data to validate our model.
- **Key findings:**
 - 21 cohort patients; Age range 31-67 yo (49 average)
 - 84 total new or previously unknown conditions detected across 9 health domains (Cardiovascular, Metabolic, Endocrine, Neurologic, Musculoskeletal, Genitourinary/Gastrointestinal, Hematologic/Immunologic, Cancer Detection, Genetics)
 - 16 incidental MRI findings, 1 critical genetic finding, 1 finding of thyroid nodule leading to a diagnosis of cancer
 - 100% of patients with actionable results as defined by program criteria
- **Modeled Cost Impact:** Using conservative, payer-relevant modeling, we estimate that early detection and closed-loop follow-up could yield net savings ranging from ~\$360 to ~\$1,500 PMPM (\approx \$4,000–\$18,000 per participant annually), even after accounting for program-triggered follow-ups and induced utilization. A base case scenario projects ~\$1,100 PMPM (~\$13,200 per participant per year). While modeled rather than observed, these figures highlight the potential of the *Wholebody Assessment* to materially reduce costs through earlier intervention, improved chronic disease management, and prevention of high-cost acute events.
- **Discussion and Conclusions:** Our novel comprehensive evaluation identified actionable health insights in all patients who participated in the program. We uncovered previously occult conditions ranging from impaired bone health to a

critical genetic cardiovascular disease. Through a multi-disciplinary approach and careful care coordination, we were able to provide both follow-through and follow-up, ensuring a closed loop system. In our cost impact model, base case cost savings of our program could reach over \$13,000 annually per participant. Early results validate the effectiveness of our *Wholebody Assessment* to surface previously undetected, actionable health insights, drive significant cost savings, and improve overall patient health.

- **Policy Context and Opportunity:** Early-diagnosis programs are scaling in the private market and among plan sponsors, but coverage and policy initiatives lag behind demand. Current rules exclude most multi-modal assessments and many emerging diagnostics, creating an access gap that pushes patients toward out-of-pocket direct-to-consumer options. A pragmatic regulatory pathway, such as targeted statutory updates with coverage-with-evidence safeguards, can expand access while generating the outcomes data policymakers require.
 - **Future Directions:** Formal launch of our *Wholebody Assessment*, collect 6 month follow-up data on our initial patients, track short-term intervention outcomes. Establishment of Commons Early-Diagnosis Value Framework (CED-VF) to demonstrate clinical validity and utility, economic impact, equity and access, and safety.
-

Introduction

Health and wellness are commonly measured in terms of *lifespan*: how long one will live. Recently, *healthspan*, the duration of a person's life spent in good health, has emerged as a more aspirational and desirable health metric. Healthspan proponents argue that living healthier late into life is preferable to simply living longer. At the same time, rising costs and inconsistent outcomes continue to place pressure on our healthcare system. We can no longer afford to be reactionary, identifying and treating illness too late in the disease process.

Patient expectations are shifting as healthcare becomes increasingly consumer driven; global wellness is now a \$2 trillion industry. According to McKinsey, the United States is responsible for \$500 billion of total wellness spending with 84% of consumers labeling wellness a “top” or “important” priority.¹ The health and wellness movement has spawned a number of solutions, each offering its own value proposition.

Consumer uptake of comprehensive, DTC early-diagnosis services has accelerated. Whole-body MRI vendors report rapid growth, multiple companies now offer comprehensive biomarker assessments, and multi-cancer early-detection (MCED) blood tests are being piloted by life insurers and selected employers as a covered benefit. Princeton University, for example, offers MCED testing with plan-defined eligibility, Point32Health piloted no-cost access for certain members, and John Hancock subsidizes MCED for eligible life insurance customers.² These real-world adoption signals suggest strong product–market fit, particularly among mid-life adults who value earlier risk stratification and closed-loop follow-through.

The clinical and financial impact of these solutions is unproven. Integration with the traditional healthcare system remains a challenge as providers struggle to parse external data. Comprehensive lab testing and imaging raises concerns about overdiagnosis and overtreatment. Several companies offer access to a “clinical team,” but the capabilities, credentials, and consistency of such teams is unclear. follow-up may be delivered through heuristic dashboards, artificial intelligence tools, or referral to a patient’s primary care provider.

Healthspan can be viewed as the confluence of prevention, lifestyle modification, and social drivers. Each of these components of health plays a critical role in determining the amount of time spent in good health. However, full realization of the *healthspan* ideal requires thoughtful integration of early detection and focused interventions. Insights surfaced through comprehensive testing should be paired with prescriptive action plans, careful coordination with primary care providers, and access to a high quality, vetted network of specialists (when required). With that ethos in mind, Commons Clinic

developed the *Wholebody Assessment*, a comprehensive health and wellness evaluation. The program combines advanced diagnostics, consultation with a multi-disciplinary team, and dedicated treatment plans to create a “closed loop” system.

This white paper presents the early findings from Commons Clinic’s comprehensive *Wholebody Assessment* initial patient cohort. Our objective is to highlight initial observations including detected conditions, subsequent interventions, and lessons learned. We will also explore the potential cost savings associated with this program, how it complements traditional primary care, our approach to incidental findings, and the prospective next steps for the program’s development.

Methods

Patient Demographics

The initial cohort included 21 patients with an average age of 49 years (range 31-67). There were 11 male patients and 10 female patients. The average number of baseline health conditions in the cohort was 2.5 with 1.33 prescription medications per patient. Body mass index (BMI) in our sample ranged from 19.7 to 35.8 (average 26.2).

Program Design

The *Wholebody Assessment* was structured as a multi-step process designed to provide a comprehensive health evaluation, facilitate early detection and intervention via advanced diagnostics, and generate actionable health strategies for each participant.

Pre-Visit Preparation

- Patients received detailed preparation instructions including fasting requirements and activity guidelines.
- Laboratory testing was initiated in advance through a partnership with GetLabs, which arranged at-home blood draws approximately two weeks prior to the on-site assessment.
- The care team reviewed initial lab results before the assessment day, ensuring a personalized and efficient visit.

Assessment Day

All remaining diagnostic studies and consultative evaluations were conducted in a single, coordinated visit at Commons Clinic's Santa Monica location. Assessments included:

- **Advanced imaging and diagnostics:**
 - Full body MRI*
 - Coronary Artery Calcium scoring*
 - DEXA bone density scanning*
 - Body composition analysis
 - Cardiopulmonary testing (resting 12-lead EKG, VO2 Max)
*performed off-site through a preferred imaging partner

- **Functional and musculoskeletal evaluation:**
 - Mobility assessment
 - Strength testing
 - Injury risk scoring

- **Neurocognitive and wellness screening:**
 - Cognitive testing
 - Sleep health screen
 - Mental health questionnaires
 - Vision screening

- **Specialist-led consultations:**
 - Same day nutritionist and physical therapy assessments
 - Integrated, team-based approach
 - Immediate, practical recommendations

Results Review

Following completion of testing, patients engaged in one-on-one consultation with the Wholebody physician (a fellowship-trained Cardiologist), who synthesized results across multiple body systems. This session emphasized education, risk stratification, and personalized interpretation of findings.

Personalized Action Plan

Each participant received a structured, prioritized action plan for ongoing care, including:

- Recommended follow-up testing or specialist referral.

- Nutrition, mobility, and exercise strategies.

- Lifestyle modifications to support long-term health and disease prevention.

Follow-Up Care

After the initial consultation, all patients received close follow-up through several channels:

- Each patient was provided with two sessions: one with the physician for results review and care coordination, and one with a dietitian to reinforce the individualized plan of care. Follow-up was conducted primarily through telehealth (video visit) per patient preference.
- The program physician coordinated additional testing as needed and shared relevant findings with the patient's primary care provider or existing specialists to support continuity of care.
- Patients were offered the option to continue with extended nutrition, PT, or specialist engagement for a comprehensive, longitudinal care pathway.

Actions

The *Wholebody Assessment* program translated diagnostic findings into personalized interventions across multiple domains. Nearly all patients required some form of follow-up, underscoring the program's ability to uncover actionable health insights in a mid-age population that might otherwise go undetected.

Lifestyle Modification & Nutrition Support

- Patients with hyperlipidemia, fatty liver disease, obesity/visceral fat, elevated CRP, and vitamin D deficiency were guided toward structured dietary counseling, supplementation protocols, and exercise-based interventions.
- All patients in our initial cohort received formal nutrition consults with tailored meal planning and supplement review.

Specialist Referral

- **Cardiology:** Patients with abnormal coronary artery calcium (CAC) scores, moderate to severe lipid derangements, uncontrolled long-standing hypertension, and ARVD mutation were referred for cardiology consultation.
- **Endocrinology:** Thyroid abnormalities, hormone deficiencies, and metabolic irregularities prompted endocrine review and referral.

- **Gastroenterology/Hepatology:** Findings of fatty liver disease, iron imbalance, and a renal lesion triggered further specialist input.
- **Hematology/Genetics:** Factor V Leiden, hereditary hemochromatosis mutations, and other carrier states warranted hematology and genetic counseling.

Physical Therapy & Musculoskeletal Interventions

- Patients with osteopenia were counseled on bone health, nutrition, and exercise strategies.
- Those with PT findings (asymmetries, pain, mobility concerns) were given corrective therapy and targeted strength/mobility programs.

Preventative Counseling

- Genetic risk findings (e.g. APOE variants, HFE and Triadin Knockout carrier status) were used to provide education and preventive strategies, particularly around long-term dementia risk and family planning.

Definitions and Safeguards

We defined "actionable" results a priori as findings that triggered:

- Medication initiation/adjustment
- Guideline-concordant referral
- Prescribed therapeutic exercise or nutrition plan with measurable targets; or
- A diagnostic confirmation step

We developed an incidental-finding protocol (multidisciplinary review, patient communication, recommended next steps, and documentation) to mitigate over-testing harms. We will prospectively register the ongoing evaluation plan and apply a uniform cost-modeling approach that counts both cost offsets (e.g., avoided admissions) and induced utilization (follow-up imaging, specialist visits).

Disclaimer

The analysis presented here was conducted using de-identified, aggregated information from patients who voluntarily participated in Commons Clinic's Wholebody Assessment. Data collection and reporting were undertaken for the purposes of program evaluation and quality improvement, not for the generation of generalizable scientific knowledge. In

accordance with federal guidance, this project does not constitute human subjects research and was not subject to IRB review. Should future dissemination in a peer-reviewed journal be pursued, Commons Clinic will seek a determination of Institutional Review Board (IRB) approval.

Conditions Detected and Interventions

The initial phase of the *Wholebody Assessment* revealed a range of conditions, often at early stages, enabling timely interventions.

Table 1. Conditions and Interventions

Condition Category	New Cases Detected	Examples of Conditions	Actions Taken	Potential Cost Savings
Cardiovascular	14	Hyperlipidemia, coronary calcification requiring lipid lowering medication initiation or intensification	Lifestyle modifications, medication adjustments, specialist referrals	\$23,040/CV-related hospitalization ³
Metabolic	8	Fatty liver disease, obesity, elevated CRP	Dietary counseling, exercise prescriptions, ongoing monitoring	\$3,087/yr annual medical cost for BMI ⁴
Endocrine	25	Vitamin D deficiency, Supplement toxicity, hypothyroidism, thyroid nodule	Biopsy, further imaging, specialist consultation	\$460-\$2,555 per patient per year hypothyroidism related medical costs ⁵
Neurological	2	Increased dementia risk (ApoE)	Cognitive assessments, neurologist referrals, lifestyle recommendations	
Musculoskeletal	21	Osteopenia, arthralgia, muscle weakness	Physical therapy, orthopedic consultations, pain management	\$44,311/yr per fragility fracture ⁶

Condition Category	New Cases Detected	Examples of Conditions	Actions Taken	Potential Cost Savings
Gastrointestinal/ Genitourinary & Reproductive	5	Renal lesions	Additional imaging (CT, ultrasound)	
Hematologic/ Immunologic	1	Low ferritin	H. Pylori tested and confirmed, underwent treatment	
Cancer detection	1	Bilateral thyroid nodules leading to diagnosis of thyroid cancer	Ultrasound, Biopsy	
Genetic	7	ARVD Mutation - Dominant,, G6PD Deficiency, Factor V Leiden Thrombophilia, Carrier for HFE, Carrier Triadin Knockout Syndrome	Referral to Cardiology, Hematology, and Genetic consultations, cascade testing of all first degree family members	
Total	84			

Incidental Findings

Given the comprehensive nature and advanced diagnostics offered by our program, developing a repeatable approach to addressing incidental findings was paramount. We established a structured, reproducible protocol for handling unexpected findings, ensuring patient safety, minimizing anxiety, and providing appropriate follow-up. Our process includes:

1. **Clinical Review:** All incidental findings underwent thorough clinical review by a multidisciplinary team including a board-certified physician.
2. **Patient Communication:** Findings were communicated to patients with clear explanations and recommendations, the ability to ask follow-up questions, and shared decision-making.

3. **Referral for Specialist Evaluation:** Patients with clinically significant incidental findings were promptly referred to appropriate specialists for further evaluation and management.
4. **Documentation:** All findings, communications, and follow-up actions were meticulously documented in the patient's health record.

We detected three incidental findings requiring further workup: bilateral thyroid nodules, a possible adrenal mass, and a parotid mass, all identified on whole-body MRI imaging. The thyroid nodules underwent ultrasound evaluation followed by biopsy which revealed the presence of malignancy. Expedited oncology follow-up was coordinated by the *Wholebody* team. A questionable adrenal mass was detected on MRI but not subsequently seen on follow-up CT imaging, likely due to poor imaging acquisition due to adjacent respiratory movement of the diaphragm. A parotid mass was still pending evaluation at the time of the creation of this document.

Thirteen incidental findings not requiring additional work up were detected: 7 patients with hepatic cysts, 2 patients with renal cysts and other findings as below (Table 2) which did not warrant further investigation.

Table 2. Incidental Findings

	Cases Detected	Condition	Action Taken
Incidental findings requiring no work up	13	7 patients with hepatic cysts 2 patients with renal cysts 1 spinal hemangioma 1 pulmonary cyst 1 small hiatal hernia 1 parotid gland cyst	n/a
Incidental findings requiring work up	3	Bilateral thyroid nodules Questionable adrenal mass Parotid mass	Thyroid ultrasound followed by biopsy CT imaging revealed no mass Pending advanced imaging

Lessons Learned

The initial cohort provided valuable insights that will shape the future of the *Wholebody Assessment*. Key lessons include:

- **Importance of personalized follow-up:** While the assessment provides comprehensive data, the effectiveness of interventions is heavily dependent on individualized follow-up plans. Care coordination including direct communication with established medical teams and directed specialty referrals is critical to success.
 - **Patient engagement:** Active patient participation and understanding of their results are crucial for adherence to recommended actions.
 - **Streamlined referral pathways:** Establishing clear and efficient pathways for specialist referrals significantly improves the speed of necessary interventions.
 - **Data integration challenges:** Integrating diverse data points from various assessment modalities requires robust technological solutions for comprehensive patient profiles. Leveraging our in-house artificial intelligence tool, CommonsAI, will enhance efficiency, data synthesis, and patient communication.
 - **Imaging quality control:** High quality image acquisition is critical to differentiating between clinically relevant and incidental findings. To that end, we have sought relationships with imaging partners who can provide consistently high quality imaging and interpretation.
-

Modeled Cost Impact

A frequent criticism of early detection and intervention programs is their unclear value proposition and their potential to unnecessarily increase downstream healthcare costs. To address this concern, we applied a conservative, payer-relevant model to estimate the budget impact of identifying and treating conditions earlier:

- **Unit costs:** Assigned standard episode or annual costs from recent Medicare/claims literature to each actionable diagnosis (e.g., cardiovascular admissions, hypothyroidism, fragility fractures).
- **Attribution:** Counted only the fraction of downstream costs plausibly avoidable within 12–24 months.
- **Induced utilization:** Subtracted costs of follow-up testing, specialty consults, and procedures triggered by our program.
- **Outputs:** Reported results as both per-patient and per-member-per-month (PMPM).

Illustrative Findings

- **Early endocrine intervention:** Our cohort revealed 25 previously undiagnosed endocrine conditions including several instances of hypothyroidism. The direct and indirect economic burden of hypothyroidism is estimated at **\$460–\$2,555 per patient per year**.⁵ Left untreated, hypothyroidism can drive higher cholesterol, cardiovascular disease, and neuropathy. By detecting such conditions early, our program created opportunities for cost-effective treatment before complications arose.
- **Avoiding costly acute events:** Fragility fractures remain one of the most expensive sequelae of osteoporosis, with an average annual cost of **\$44,311 per case**.⁶ Yet many at-risk patients are never screened. Our initial cohort found several cases of treatable osteopenia, representing a meaningful opportunity to prevent future fractures, associated hospitalizations, and patient morbidity.
- **Optimizing cardiovascular management:** Cardiovascular disease is the leading cost driver in U.S. healthcare with each hospitalization averaging **\$23,040**.³ Our 21-patient sample uncovered 14 cardiovascular conditions, many previously undiagnosed. Early risk stratification and initiation of therapy (e.g., statins,

antihypertensives, lifestyle programs) can reduce hospitalization rates, improve outcomes, and deliver measurable savings.

Modeled Net Impact Scenarios

Gross offsets across the 21 participants totaled **\$1.55 million (~\$73,600 per participant, or \$6,317 PMPM)**. To reflect real-world uptake and induced utilization, we modeled conservative net scenarios:

Table 3. Modeled Cost Savings

Attribution	Induced Utilization	Net PMPM	Net per participant (12 mo)
10%	\$500	\$527	\$6,864
	\$1,500	\$489	\$5,864
	\$3,000	\$364	\$4,364
20%	\$500	\$1,186	\$14,229
	\$1,500	\$1,102	\$13,229
	\$3,000	\$977	\$11,729
25%	\$500	\$1,493	\$17,911
	\$1,500	\$1,409	\$16,911
	\$3,000	\$1,284	\$15,911

Takeaway

Even under low attribution (10%) and higher induced utilization rates (\$3,000), the model shows a positive net impact (~\$364 PMPM). In a base case (20% attribution, \$1,500 induced), the program yields **~\$1,100 PMPM or ~\$13,200 per participant annually**.

These results are modeled, not observed, but serve to illustrate the potential cost savings

achieved through our program's early detection and intervention of otherwise occult conditions.

Complement to Primary Care

The Wholebody Comprehensive Health Assessment is designed to be highly complementary to, rather than a replacement for, primary care. The program offers patients a 360-degree view of their health as an adjunct to their annual physical. Communication and coordination with patients' established medical teams was a core component of our offering with a focus on ensuring continuity of care. The program is synergistic with primary care through:

- **Enhanced diagnostic capabilities:** The assessment provides a detailed health snapshot that augments the diagnostic scope of routine primary care visits.
 - **Foundation building for ongoing care:** Findings from the assessment can inform and enrich the ongoing relationship between patients and their primary care providers.
 - **Specialized insights:** Wholebody offers specialized insights that can guide primary care physicians in making more targeted referrals and treatment decisions.
-

Discussion

Comprehensive health assessments are not new. Japan's Ningen Dock, a health checkup system that includes a battery of tests and evaluations, was developed as an adjunct to the country's universal health insurance system.⁷ The program focuses on early cancer detection, identification of lifestyle-related diseases, and confirmation of health status. Although the cost of participation is borne by the patient, 3.7 million people opt to pay out-of-pocket for Ningen Dock annually. The program is believed to contribute to Japan's superior life expectancy. The popularity of the program has led to an increase in medical tourism to the country.

Meanwhile, American healthcare is often criticized for being a reactive "sick care" system, tuned for treating problems as they arise rather than intervening early in the disease process. Early intervention has been demonstrated to improve outcomes and reduce costs. The "Million Hearts Model" encouraged and paid for cardiovascular disease risk assessment and reduction, resulting in fewer first-time heart attacks and strokes.⁸

Handelsman et al. argue that traditional healthcare's stepwise approach "promotes clinical inertia and the inability to reach goals, in turn contributing to increased morbidity and mortality." Instead, they propose a system built on early diagnosis and prompt intervention that facilitates faster goal attainment and improved outcomes.⁹

Early detection and intervention for chronic conditions has also been shown to result in significant cost savings. Thomas et al. reported potential savings of £68 billion (\$92 billion) with 4.9 million QALYs gained and 3.4 million cases of CVD prevented over 25 years with improved detection and management of six high risk diagnoses.¹⁰ In our sample calculation, aggregated potential cost savings across the Wholebody program totalled \$1.55 million, or around \$71,000 per patient. At an average yearly cost of \$14,750 per patient, our program could offset almost 5 years of healthcare spending. With costs for employer coverage expected to surge on average ~9.5% in 2026¹¹ and looming Medicare insolvency, reducing medical expenditure is paramount.

The Commons Clinic *Wholebody Assessment* builds upon these principles, offering a systems-based approach with incorporation of advanced testing. Like Ningen Dock, the goal of the program is to improve health outcomes through early detection and intervention. While we expected to uncover heretofore undetected diagnoses, our initial results were revealing. We discovered previously undiagnosed conditions in all 21 patients comprising our initial cohort, some with multiple new diagnoses.

In total, we detected 84 cases across 9 condition categories with cardiovascular, endocrine, and musculoskeletal conditions being most common. Perhaps most strikingly, genetic testing revealed a previously unknown congenital cardiac condition. Knowledge of this finding significantly impacted the lives of the patient and their family members. We also uncovered a case of early stage thyroid cancer based on full-body MRI imaging and subsequent follow-up (ultrasound and biopsy of the lesion).

The marketplace is iterating rapidly: vendors report tens of thousands of whole-body MRI scans completed with ongoing prospective datasets, prices are falling as more offerings come to market, and MCED programs continue to expand across life insurers and selected employer populations. These trends do not establish net benefit on their own, but they demonstrate sustained consumer and sponsor demand, underscoring the need for covered pathways that require outcomes reporting and mitigate harm.

A common criticism of longevity assessments, biomarker testing, and wholebody imaging is care fragmentation, information asymmetry, and lack of follow through. A key component of our program was to foster close coordination and communication with the patient's existing care team. We facilitated follow-up for both routine and urgent clinical findings, ensuring continuity of care and turning lab results and imaging findings into actionable insights. Patients were offered the option to continue with extended nutrition,

PT, or specialist engagement for a comprehensive, longitudinal care pathway. We also developed a repeatable process for handling clinically insignificant incidental findings to reduce low yield interventions and unnecessary testing.

The salient result in our early cohort is not the count of abnormalities per se but rather the high proportion of findings tied to specific, guideline-consistent actions and closed-loop follow-through. To address concerns about overdiagnosis and care fragmentation common to DTC offerings, our model integrates cross-domain testing with immediate care plans, close communication with primary care, and tracked completion of next steps. We will report 6- and 12-month outcomes including medication initiation and persistence, verified referrals completed, repeat biomarker changes, musculoskeletal function gains, and short-term utilization (ED visits, admissions).

Future Directions

Commons Early-Diagnosis Value Framework (CED-VF)

Our initial findings serve as the foundation of an early-diagnosis value framework, informed by monitoring:

- **Clinical validity and utility:** Report detection yield, positive predictive value, and “change-in-management” rates by domain (cardiometabolic, endocrine, MSK, neuro, GI/GU, genetics). Track stage-shift where applicable and time-to-diagnosis versus usual care.
- **Economic impact:** Present per-member-per-month (PMPM) effects and 12–24-month budget impact for plans and employers, counting downstream costs from false positives and incidental findings. Anchor unit costs to Medicare fee schedules and peer-reviewed claims analyses (e.g., average CV hospitalization cost; fragility-fracture episode costs; hypothyroidism burden).
- **Safety and stewardship:** Quantify incidental-finding rates, false-positive cascades, radiation exposure (if any), repeat-scan intervals, and adherence to appropriateness thresholds.
- **Equity and access:** Monitor uptake by age, sex, race/ethnicity, and payer type; report completion of follow-up steps by subgroup.

- **Operational readiness:** Use FHIR-based data export, closed-loop tracking, eConsults, and defined referral SLAs.
- **Evidence bar for coverage:** Predefine “graduation criteria” for payer coverage: actionable findings with documented plan execution, medication/referral adherence, and net PMPM savings within defined parameters.

Next Steps

Building on the success and lessons learned from the beta phase, the following next steps are planned for the Wholebody Assessment program:

- **Program Expansion:** Scale the program to accommodate a larger patient cohort.
- **Technological Enhancements:** Further develop data integration platforms to create a more seamless patient and provider experience.
- **Longitudinal Outcome Tracking:** Establish a robust system for tracking long-term patient outcomes and cost savings.
- **Research and Publication:** Continue to collect data for ongoing research, leading to further internal reports and external publications.
- **Partnership Development:** Explore collaborations with other healthcare providers and research institutions to enhance program reach and impact.

Policy Implications

The Affordable Care Act’s Section 2713 guarantees first-dollar coverage only for preventive services with USPSTF A/B ratings; composite, multi-modal early-diagnosis programs typically fall outside this pathway.¹² Medicare may add “additional preventive services” only when strict criteria are met via national coverage determinations. As a result, access today is largely out-of-pocket or via limited employer pilots, despite growing demand and promising early outcomes. Federal action is needed to support development and implementation of these services.

Policy considerations and statutory options include:

- **Create a new preventive benefit category:** Congress should amend Section 1861 of the Social Security Act to establish a “Comprehensive Risk Assessment & Early

Detection" benefit class. This would allow CMS to cover multi-modal assessments that meet predefined evidence thresholds, use coverage-with-evidence development (CED) to generate outcomes, and apply guardrails on frequency, age/risk criteria, and follow-through requirements.

- **Modernize private-market preventive coverage:** Congress should direct the Departments (HHS, Labor, Treasury) and the USPSTF to pilot an "Integrated Preventive Service" rating for bundled, cross-domain assessments that meet effectiveness and harm-mitigation standards, enabling Section 2713 no-cost coverage decisions for services that cannot be evaluated as single tests.
- **Extend HDHP/HSA preventive safe harbor:** Treasury's safe harbor already allows some pre-deductible coverage for chronic-condition care. Congress should extend the safe harbor to risk-stratified early-diagnosis bundles that meet evidence benchmarks, allowing employers to cover these services pre-deductible without jeopardizing HSA eligibility.
- **Leverage CMS TCET + CED for diagnostics:** CMS's Transitional Coverage for Emerging Technologies (TCET) pathway can be adapted to cover multi-component preventive diagnostics, tying national coverage to active evidence generation and real-world outcomes reporting with sunset clauses if endpoints are not met.¹³
- **Regulatory clarity for lab-developed tests:** The FDA's 2024 Laboratory Developed Tests (LDT) rule was vacated by a federal district court in March 2025, creating near-term uncertainty.¹⁴ Congress can resolve this by directing a risk-based framework focused on analytical/clinical validity and post-market surveillance for high-impact preventive tests used in covered programs.
- **Equity guardrails:** Any new benefit should require transparent reporting by age/sex/race/ethnicity, fund navigation for abnormal results, and include limits on scan/test frequency and appropriateness criteria to reduce low-value cascades.

Conclusion

The results of our initial cohort of Wholebody Assessment patients suggest a significant opportunity to improve outcomes and reduce costs through early detection and intervention. A 2007 analysis by Falagas et al. found that the underdiagnosis of common chronic diseases in the developed world ranges from 20% for dementia to 90% for depression and osteoarthritis.¹⁵ All patients in our cohort had previously undiagnosed

medical conditions, several with multiple conditions. With growing appreciation of *healthspan*, the time spent in good health, patients are increasingly interested in gaining a better understanding of their health and taking an active role in living well. Early detection and intervention are key components of reducing costs, improving outcomes, increasing *healthspan*, and ushering in a new era of American healthcare.

References

1. Pione, Anna, Jonathan Medalsy, Kristi Weaver, Shaun Callaghan, Stefan Rickert, Hayley Doner, and Jil-Marie Dahm. 2025. "The \$2 Trillion Global Wellness Market Gets a Millennial and Gen Z Glow-Up." McKinsey & Company, May 29, 2025. <https://www.mckinsey.com/industries/consumer-packaged-goods/our-insights/future-of-wellness-trends>.
2. <https://www.point32health.org/newsroom/news-media/point32health-and-grail-expand-pilot-access-to-galleri-multi-cancer-early-detection-blood-test>
3. Amier Haidar, Aryan Gajjar, Rushi V. Parikh, Peyman Benharash, Gregg C. Fonarow, Karol Watson, Jack Needleman, Boback Ziaeiian. National Costs for Cardiovascular-Related Hospitalizations and Inpatient Procedures in the United States, 2016 to 2021, *The American Journal of Cardiology*, Volume 234, 2025, Pages 63-70, ISSN 0002-9149, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.amjcard.2024.10.003>.
4. Ward ZJ, Bleich SN, Long MW, Gortmaker SL. Association of body mass index with health care expenditures in the United States by age and sex. *PLoS One*. 2021 Mar 24;16(3):e0247307. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0247307. PMID: 33760880; PMCID: PMC7990296.
5. Hepp Z, Lage MJ, Espallat R, Gossain VV. The direct and indirect economic burden of hypothyroidism in the United States: a retrospective claims database study. *J Med Econ*. 2021 Jan-Dec;24(1):440-446. doi: 10.1080/13696998.2021.1900202. PMID: 33685322.
6. Singer A, McClung MR, Tran O, Morrow CD, Goldstein S, Kagan R, McDermott M, Yehoshua A. Treatment rates and healthcare costs of patients with fragility fracture by site of care: a real-world data analysis. *Arch Osteoporos*. 2023 Mar 11;18(1):42. doi: 10.1007/s11657-023-01229-7. PMID: 36905559; PMCID: PMC10008255.
7. Jun Lu, Ninggen Dock: Japan's unique comprehensive health checkup system for early detection of disease, *Global Health & Medicine*, 2022, Volume 4, Issue 1, Pages 9-13, Released on J-STAGE March 17, 2022, Advance online publication February 24, 2022, Online ISSN 2434-9194, Print ISSN 2434-9186, <https://doi.org/10.35772/ghm.2021.01109>
8. Blue L, Kranker K, Markovitz AR, et al. Effects of the Million Hearts Model on Myocardial Infarctions, Strokes, and Medicare Spending: A Randomized Clinical Trial. *JAMA*. 2023;330(15):1437-1447. doi:10.1001/jama.2023.19597
9. Yehuda Handelsman, Javed Butler, George L. Bakris, Ralph A. DeFronzo, Gregg C. Fonarow, Jennifer B. Green, George Grunberger, James L. Januzzi, Samuel Klein, Pamela R. Kushner, Darren K. McGuire, Erin D. Michos, Javier Morales, Richard E. Pratley, Matthew R. Weir, Eugene Wright, Vivian A. Fonseca, Early intervention and intensive management of patients with diabetes, cardiorenal, and metabolic diseases,

Journal of Diabetes and its Complications, Volume 37, Issue 2, 2023, 108389, ISSN 1056-8727, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jdiacomp.2022.108389>.

10. Thomas C, Brennan A, Goka E, et al. What are the cost-savings and health benefits of improving detection and management for six high cardiovascular risk conditions in England? An economic evaluation *BMJ Open* 2020;10:e037486. doi: 10.1136/bmjopen-2020-037486.

11. <https://www.wsj.com/health/healthcare/health-insurance-costs-rise>

12. <https://www.kff.org/womens-health-policy/preventive-services-covered-by-private-health-plans/>

13. <https://www.cms.gov/newsroom/fact-sheets/final-notice-transitional-coverage-emerging-technologies-cms-3421-fn>

14. <https://www.fda.gov/medical-devices/in-vitro-diagnostics/laboratory-developed-tests>

15. Falagas ME, Vardakas KZ, Vergidis PI. Under-diagnosis of common chronic diseases: prevalence and impact on human health. *Int J Clin Pract*. 2007 Sep;61(9):1569-79. doi:

10.1111/j.1742-1241.2007.01423.x. PMID: 17686096.

For more information, please contact **ben@commonsclinic.com**